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Synthesis of Some 1-Methyl 4-Phenyl Piperidines

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MCELVAIN and Clemens¹ synthesised potent piperidine analgesics which contained alkyl and aryl substituent in the four positions. The most potent compound contained a meta-hydroxyl substituent in the aromatic ring. The analgetic activity disappeared when the hydroxyl group was introduced in the ortho or para position. Parcell² reported that some 4-(ortho-substituted phenyl)-1-hydroxyalkyl-piperidine showed hypotensive activity. To investigate pharmacological activity, a series of compounds of the type (I) has now been synthesised.

2-Alkyl-4,5-dimethoxybenzaldehyde has been prepared from 3,4-dimethoxyalkyl-benzene by formylation with POCl₃ and dimethyl formamide. 2-Alkyl-4,5-dimethoxybenzaldehyde has been treated with ethyl acetoacetate in presence of piperidine. The condensation product, a bis-acetoacetate, on hydrolysis gives 3-(2-alkyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-glutaric acid. The latter acid on heating with acetic anhydride has been converted to the corresponding glutaric anhydride. The anhydride reacts with methylamine to yield N-methyl imide. The imide on reduction with lithium aluminium hydride has yielded the desired product (I). Data of the compounds have been listed in the table.

Pharmacology: The compound (I : R = C₂H₅) in a dose of 2 mg/Kg produced a sharp and prolonged fall of blood pressure in anaesthetised cat. This fall could not be blocked by atropine or antihistaminic agent. At a very high dose (10 mg/Kg) the

TABLE

Name of the compound	Molecular formula	m.p. °C	Analysis%						IR (cm ⁻¹)
			Requires			Found			
			O	H	N	O	H	N	
1. Ethyl-2,4-diacetyl-3-(2-methyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-glutarate	C ₂₂ H ₃₀ O ₆	140	62.5	7.12	—	62.15	6.9	—	1721, 1734
2. Ethyl-2,4-diacetyl-3-(2-ethyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-glutarate	C ₂₄ H ₃₂ O ₆	135	63.3	7.33	—	63.0	7.12	—	1724, 1748
3. Ethyl-2,4-diacetyl-3-(2-n-propyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-glutarate	C ₂₆ H ₃₄ O ₆	152	64.0	7.55	—	63.5	7.05	—	1721, 1748
4. β-(2-Methyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-glutaric acid	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ O ₆	142	59.57	6.38	—	59.32	6.05	—	1695
5. β-(2-Ethyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-glutaric acid	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₆	151.5	60.81	6.75	—	60.25	6.55	—	1695
6. β-(2-n-Propyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-glutaric acid	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ O ₆	144	61.93	7.09	—	61.45	6.59	—	1695
7. β-(2-Methyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-glutaric anhydride	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₅	95	63.63	6.06	—	63.12	5.68	—	1760
8. β-(2-Ethyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-glutaric anhydride	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ O ₅	129.5	64.74	6.47	—	64.24	6.15	—	1760
9. β-(2-n-Propyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-glutaric anhydride	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₅	135	65.75	6.84	—	65.53	6.41	—	1760
10. β-(2-Methyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-N-methyl glutarimide	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ O ₄ N	158	64.98	6.85	5.05	64.54	6.35	5.1	1678
11. β-(2-Ethyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-N-methyl glutarimide	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ O ₄ N	112	65.97	7.21	4.81	65.59	7.03	4.33	1678
12. β-(2-n-Propyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-N-methyl glutarimide	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ O ₄ N	141	66.88	7.54	4.59	66.39	7.23	4.18	1678
13. 1-Methyl-4-(2-methyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-piperidine hydrochloride	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ O ₂ NCl	250	63.04	8.4	4.9	62.51	8.87	5.34	—
14. 1-Methyl-4-(2-ethyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-piperidine hydrochloride	C ₁₈ H ₂₆ O ₂ NCl	240	64.1	8.01	4.67	64.27	8.52	4.95	—
15. 1-Methyl-4-(2-n-propyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-piperidine hydrochloride	C ₂₀ H ₂₈ O ₂ NCl	178	65.07	8.93	4.46	65.90	9.30	4.77	—

compound, however, had a relaxation effect on G. I. T. The depressor effect of the compound could be of some central action.

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Synthesis of 2,3,8,9-tetrasubstituted diimidazo [2',3'-b : 2'',3''-b''] benzo [1,2-d : 4,5-d'] bithiazolo-5,11-diones—Possible Pesticides

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HETEROCYCLES containing thiazole and imidazole rings have been successfully screened as anti-protozoal agents¹, anticonvulsants² and anti-diabetics³. The title compounds incorporate

has been well stressed^{4, 5} in many pesticides. Keeping the above in view, the title compounds have been synthesised with the hope that they might be pesticides of choice.

We have previously described the synthesis of thiadiazolobenzimidazoles⁶, thiazolinediones⁷, imidazolinediones⁸. The present paper deals with the synthesis of some new diimidazo-dithiazolo diones by condensing chloranil with cyclic thioureas. The products isolated were 2,3,8,9-tetrasubstituted diimidazo [2',3'-b : 2'',3''-b''] benzo [1,2-d : 4,5-d'] bithiazolo-5, 11-diones (I). All compounds of this

series gave characteristic red colour with conc. H₂SO₄.

The infrared spectra of compounds (I) showed characteristic bands at 1680-1690 (C=O), 1610-1620 (C=N) and 1065-1075, 665-675 cm⁻¹ (C-S) respectively⁹. The uv spectra of each compound showed three bands with large extinction values. Absorption at longer wavelengths in these compounds can be ascribed to the fact that there is a larger scope for electronic excitation due to resonance. The presence of group R, R₁ does not produce significant bathochromic shift.

(I)

Experimental

All melting points were determined on a Kofler Instrument and are uncorrected. IR spectra were determined on a Perkin-Elmer 677 Spectrophotometer in KBr. UV absorption spectra were recorded on a Beckman spectrophotometer Model DU-2 using 1 cm path length quartz cells.

Cyclic thioureas : The compounds were prepared by known methods^{10,11}.

2,3,8,9-tetrasubstituted diimidazo [2',3'-b : 2'',3''-b''] benzo [1,2-d : 4,5-d'] bithiazolo-5,11-diones (I) : A mixture of chloranil (0.1 mole) and cyclic thiourea (0.2 mole) in 25 ml ethanol was heated under reflux for 4 hrs. The reaction mixture was cooled basified with ammonia and again refluxed for 5 minutes. The solid separated on cooling was filtered dried and recrystallised twice from aq. ethanol. The purity of the products was established by tlc. The analysis, m.p., ir data etc. are given in Table 1.

Herbicidal screening :

Herbicidal activity was evaluated by pre-emergence tests at three concentrations viz., 1000, 100 and 10 ppm against *Argemone mexicana* and *Cyperus rotundus*. The number of replications in each case was three. Seeds/tubers of the test plants were

TABLE 1—2,3,8,9-TETRASUBSTITUTED-DIIMIDAZO[2',3'-b : 2'',3''-b'']BENZO[1,2-d : 4,5-d']BISTHIAZOLO-5,11-DIONES

Sl. No.	R	R ₁	Molecular formula	Yield %	m.p. °C	% Analysis		UV data		IR data
						Calcd.	Found	Ethanol		
								λ _{max} nm	log ε	
1.	H	H	C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₄ S ₂ O ₂	37	331 (decomp)	C, 47.3	46.8	281	4.56	C=O 1685, C=N 1620
						H, 2.6	2.2	305	4.30	C-S 1970, 665 cm ⁻¹
						N, 18.4	18.1	455	4.12	
2.	CH ₃	CH ₃	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₄ S ₂ O ₂	43	338	C, 55.4	55.0	273	4.41	C=O 1660, C=N 1615
						H, 3.4	3.1	314	4.27	C-S 1065, 670 cm ⁻¹
						N, 16.1	15.7	456	4.15	
3.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	C ₂₀ H ₁₀ N ₄ S ₂ O ₂	45	285	C, 70.3	69.8	277	4.32	C=O 1690, C=N 1610
						H, 3.2	2.8	309	4.18	C-S 1075, 675 cm ⁻¹
						N, 9.1	8.7	447	3.97	